

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for GPNMB (UniProt ID: Q14956) for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence

Riham Ayoubi¹, Charles Alende^{†1}, Maryam Fotouhi^{†1}, Sara González Bolívar¹, Vera Ruíz Moleón¹, and Carl Laflamme^{1*}, NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group and ABIF consortium

[†] Authors contributed equally

¹ Department of Neurology and Neurosurgery, Structural Genomics Consortium, The Montreal Neurological Institute, McGill University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada

* Corresponding author: carl.laflamme@mcgill.ca

Abstract

GPNMB, a transmembrane protein mostly expressed in immune cells, regulates inflammation response and tissue repair, with increased levels linked to neurodegenerative diseases, suggesting its potential as a biomarker. Here we have characterized twenty GPNMB commercial antibodies for western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. These studies are part of a larger, collaborative initiative seeking to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercially available antibodies for human proteins and publishing the results openly as a resource for the scientific community. While use of antibodies and protocols vary between laboratories, we encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibodies for their specific needs.

Keywords:

UniProt ID: Q14956, *GPNMB*, GPNMB, transmembrane glycoprotein NMB, glycoprotein nonmetastatic melanoma B, Osteoactivin, antibody characterization, antibody validation, western blot, immunoprecipitation, immunofluorescence

Introduction

Transmembrane glycoprotein NMB (GPNMB) is a type I transmembrane glycoprotein involved in inflammation (1), cellular differentiation (2), and tissue repair (3). It is highly expressed in microglia, macrophages (4), and astrocytes (5) and has been linked to neurodegenerative diseases, especially amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (6), Alzheimer's (7), and Parkinson's diseases (8). GPNMB expression is often elevated in response to neuroinflammation and has shown a protective role in models of neurodegeneration by potentially reducing oxidative stress (9) and promoting autophagy (3). Increased GPNMB levels are also observed in the cerebrospinal fluid of patients with neurodegenerative diseases, suggesting it could serve as a potential biomarker for disease progression (10).

This research is part of a broader collaborative initiative in which academics, funders and commercial antibody manufacturers are working together to address antibody reproducibility issues by characterizing commercial antibodies for human proteins using standardized protocols, and openly sharing the data (11-13). Here we evaluated the performance of twenty commercial antibodies for GPNMB for use in western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence, enabling biochemical and cellular assessment of GPNMB properties and function. The platform for antibody characterization used to carry out this study was endorsed by a committee of industry and academic representatives. It consists of identifying human cell lines with adequate target protein expression and the development/contribution of equivalent knockout (KO) cell lines, followed by antibody characterization procedures using most commercially available antibodies against the corresponding protein. The standardized consensus antibody characterization protocols are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (14).

The authors do not engage in result analysis or offer explicit antibody recommendations. Our primary aim is to deliver top-tier data to the scientific community, grounded in Open Science principles. This empowers experts to interpret the characterization data independently, enabling them to make informed choices regarding the most suitable antibodies for their specific experimental needs. Guidelines on how to interpret antibody characterization data found in this study are featured on the YCharOS gateway (15).

Results and discussion

Our standard protocol involves comparing readouts from parental and KO cell lines (14, 16). In the absence of commercially available KO cell lines, siRNA technology is used to knockdown (KD) the target gene (17, 18). To determine which cell line demonstrates high expression of GPNMB and thus be appropriate for KD, the first step is to identify a cell line(s) that expresses sufficient levels of a given protein to generate a measurable signal using antibodies. To this end, we examined the DepMap (Cancer Dependency Map Portal, RRID:SCR_017655) transcriptomics database to identify a cell line that expresses the target at levels greater than $2.5 \log_2$ (transcripts per million "TPM"+1), which we have found to be a suitable cut-off (11). The U-87 MG expresses the GPNMB transcript at 6.7 TPM, which is above the average range of cancer cells analyzed. A non-targeting control siRNA pool was used to treat U-87 MG control (ctrl) cells, while GPNMB was KD using a pool of siRNA targeting this gene.

To screen all antibodies by western blot, U-87 MG ctrl and *GPNMB* KD protein lysates were ran on SDS-PAGE, transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes, and then probed with twenty GPNMB antibodies in parallel (Figure 1).

We then assessed the capability of all twenty antibodies to capture GPNMB from U-87 MG protein extracts using immunoprecipitation techniques, followed by western blot analysis. For the immunoblot step, a specific GPNMB antibody identified previously (refer to Figure 1) was selected. Equal amounts of the starting material (SM) and the unbound fractions (UB), as well as the whole immunoprecipitate (IP) eluates were separated by SDS-PAGE (Figure 2).

For immunofluorescence, twenty antibodies were screened using a mosaic strategy. First, U-87 MG ctrl and *GPNMB* KD cells were labelled with different fluorescent dyes in order to distinguish the two cell lines, and the GPNMB antibodies were evaluated. Both ctrl and KD cells were imaged in the same field of view to reduce staining, imaging and image analysis bias (Figure 3). Quantification of immunofluorescence intensity in hundreds of ctrl and KD cells was performed for each antibody tested, and the images presented in Figure 3 are representative of this analysis (14).

In conclusion, we have screened twenty GPNMB commercial antibodies by western blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence by comparing the signal produced by the antibodies in human U-87 MG ctrl and *GPNMB* KD cells. To assist users in interpreting antibody performance, Table 3 outlines various scenarios in which antibodies may perform in all three applications (11). Several high-quality and renewable antibodies that successfully detect GPNMB were identified in all applications. Researchers who wish to study GPNMB in a different species are encouraged to select high-quality antibodies, based on the results of this study, and investigate the predicted species reactivity of the manufacturer before extending their research.

Limitations

Inherent limitations are associated with the antibody characterization platform used in this study. Firstly, the YCharOS project focuses on renewable (recombinant and monoclonal) antibodies and does not test all commercially available GPNMB antibodies. YCharOS partners provide approximately 80% of all renewable antibodies, but some top-cited polyclonal antibodies may not be available through these partners.

Secondly, the YCharOS effort employs a non-biased approach that is agnostic to the protein for which antibodies have been characterized. The aim is to provide objective data on antibody performance without preconceived notions about how antibodies should perform or the molecular weight that should be observed in western blot. As the authors are not experts in GPNMB, only a brief overview of the protein's function and its relevance in disease is provided. GPNMB experts are invited to analyze and interpret the observed banding patterns in western blots and the subcellular localization in immunofluorescence.

Thirdly, YCharOS experiments are not performed in replicates primarily due to the use of multiple antibodies targeting various epitopes. Once a specific antibody is identified, it validates the protein expression of the intended target in the selected cell line, confirms the lack of protein expression in the KO cell line and supports conclusions regarding the specificity of the other antibodies. Moreover, in some cases, the same antibody clones are donated by 2 manufacturers (cross-licensed antibodies), effectively serving as replicates and enabling the validation of test reproducibility. All experiments are performed using master mixes, and meticulous attention is paid to sample preparation and experimental execution. In IF, the use of two different concentrations serves to evaluate antibody specificity and can aid in assessing assay reliability. In instances where antibodies yield no signal, a repeat experiment is conducted following titration. Additionally, our independent data is performed subsequently to the antibody manufacturers internal validation process, therefore making our characterization process a repeat.

Lastly, as comprehensive and standardized procedures are respected, any conclusions remain confined to the experimental conditions and cell line used for this study. The use of a single cell type for evaluating antibody performance poses as a limitation, as factors such as target protein abundance significantly impact results (14). Additionally, the use of cancer cell lines containing gene mutations poses a potential challenge, as these mutations may be within the epitope coding sequence or other regions of the gene responsible for the intended target. Such alterations can impact the binding affinity of antibodies. This represents an inherent limitation of any approach that employs cancer cell lines.

Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocol Exchange, a preprint server (DOI:[10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1](https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.pex-2607/v1)) (14). Brief descriptions of the experimental setup used to carry out this study can be found below.

Cell lines and antibodies

Cell lines used and primary antibodies tested in this study are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. To ensure that the cell lines and antibodies are cited properly and can be easily identified, we have included their corresponding Research Resource Identifiers, or RRID (19, 20). To knockdown *GPNMB*, U-87 MG cells were treated with the *GPNMB* SMARTPool from Horizon Discovery (cat. number L-011741-01) for five days. U-87 MG control cells were treated with the ON-TARGETplus Non-targeting Control Pool (Horizon Discovery (cat. number. D-001810-10). Lipofectamine RNAiMAX (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 13778030) was used to transfect the siRNA following the manufacturer's protocol.

Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse antibodies are (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Peroxidase-conjugated donkey anti-goat antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A15999). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-rabbit and anti-mouse secondary antibodies (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A-21429 and A-21424). Alexa-555-conjugated donkey anti-goat secondary antibody is from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A-21432). Peroxidase-conjugated Protein A for IP detection is from Cell Signaling Technology, cat. number 12291.

Antibody screening by western blot

U-87 MG ctrl and *GPNMB* KD cells were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 89901) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at $\sim 110,000 \times g$ for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and western blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder (GeneDireX, cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual western blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) (Cell Signalling Technology, cat. number 9997). Following three

washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes were incubated with Pierce ECL (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate (Bio-Rad, cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg of antibody to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with 30 µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse and goat antibodies) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Two antibodies were at unknown concentrations and the following volumes were tested in the IP: 10 µl of antibody ab227695** and 20 µl of antibody 13251**. Tubes were rocked for ~1h at 4°C followed by two washes to remove unbound antibodies.

U-87 MG WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates were rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000 x g for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1h at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and western blot on precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels. Protein A:HRP was used as a secondary detection system at a concentration of 0.5 µg/ml.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

U-87 MG ctrl and *GPNMB* KD cells were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number C2925 and C34565). The nuclei were labelled with DAPI (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. Number D3571) fluorescent stain. Ctrl and KD cells were plated on 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator at 37°C, 5% CO₂. Cells were fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (VWR, cat. number 100503-917) in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) (Wisent, cat. number 311-010-CL). Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP151-500) for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum (Gibco, cat. number 16210-064) and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary GPNMB antibodies overnight at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with

395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa-555 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification (21). Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Grant information

This work was supported by a grant from the Emory-Sage-SGC TaRget Enablement to Accelerate Therapy Development for Alzheimer's Disease (TREAT-AD) center established by the National Institute on Aging (grant no. U54AG065187) and by the Government of Canada through Genome Canada, Genome Quebec, and Ontario Genomics (grant no. OGI-210). RA is supported by a Mitacs fellowship.

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Competing interests

For this project, the laboratory of Peter McPherson developed partnerships with high-quality antibody manufacturers and KO cell line providers. The partners provide antibodies and KO cell lines to the McPherson laboratory at no cost. These partners include: - Abcam-ABCD antibodies- ABclonal- Aviva Systems Biology -Bio Techne -Cell Signalling Technology -Developmental Studies Hybridoma Bank - GeneTex – Horizon Discovery – Proteintech – Synaptic Systems –Thermo Fisher Scientific.

Acknowledgment

We would like to thank the NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group for their important contribution to the creation of an open scientific ecosystem of antibody manufacturers and KO cell line suppliers, for the development of community-agreed protocols, and for their shared ideas, resources, and collaboration. Members of the group can be found below. We would also like to thank the Advanced BioImaging Facility (ABIF) consortium for their image analysis pipeline development and conduction (RRID:SCR_017697). Members of each group can be found below.

NeuroSGC/YCharOS/EDDU collaborative group: Thomas M. Durcan, Aled M. Edwards, Peter S. McPherson, Chetan Raina and Wolfgang Reintsch

ABIF consortium: Claire M. Brown and Joel Ryan

Thank you to the Structural Genomics Consortium, a registered charity (no. 1097737), for your support on this project. The Structural Genomics Consortium receives funding from Bayer AG, Boehringer Ingelheim, Bristol-Myers Squibb, Genentech, Genome Canada through Ontario Genomics Institute (grant no. OGI-196), the EU and EFPIA through the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking (EUbOPEN grant no. 875510), Janssen, Merck KGaA (also known as EMD in Canada and the United States), Pfizer and Takeda.

References

1. Gillett DA, Wallings RL, Uriarte Huarte O, Tansey MG. Progranulin and GPNMB: interactions in endo-lysosome function and inflammation in neurodegenerative disease. *J Neuroinflammation*. 2023;20(1):286.
2. Xie R, Okita Y, Ichikawa Y, Fikry MA, Huynh Dam KT, Tran STP, et al. Role of the kringle-like domain in glycoprotein NMB for its tumorigenic potential. *Cancer Sci*. 2019;110(7):2237-46.
3. Li B, Castano AP, Hudson TE, Nowlin BT, Lin SL, Bonventre JV, et al. The melanoma-associated transmembrane glycoprotein Gpnmb controls trafficking of cellular debris for degradation and is essential for tissue repair. *FASEB J*. 2010;24(12):4767-81.
4. Yu B, Sondag GR, Malcuit C, Kim MH, Safadi FF. Macrophage-Associated Osteoactivin/GPNMB Mediates Mesenchymal Stem Cell Survival, Proliferation, and Migration Via a CD44-Dependent Mechanism. *J Cell Biochem*. 2016;117(7):1511-21.
5. Neal ML, Boyle AM, Budge KM, Safadi FF, Richardson JR. The glycoprotein GPNMB attenuates astrocyte inflammatory responses through the CD44 receptor. *J Neuroinflammation*. 2018;15(1):73.
6. Tanaka H, Shimazawa M, Kimura M, Takata M, Tsuruma K, Yamada M, et al. The potential of GPNMB as novel neuroprotective factor in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Sci Rep*. 2012;2:573.
7. Huttenrauch M, Ogorek I, Klafki H, Otto M, Stadelmann C, Weggen S, et al. Glycoprotein NMB: a novel Alzheimer's disease associated marker expressed in a subset of activated microglia. *Acta Neuropathol Commun*. 2018;6(1):108.
8. International Parkinson's Disease Genomics C, Wellcome Trust Case Control C. A two-stage meta-analysis identifies several new loci for Parkinson's disease. *PLoS Genet*. 2011;7(6):e1002142.
9. Wang Q, Kuroda Y, Yang L, Lai S, Mizutani Y, Iddamalgoda A, et al. GPNMB Extracellular Fragment Protects Melanocytes from Oxidative Stress by Inhibiting AKT Phosphorylation Independent of CD44. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2021;22(19).
10. Aichholzer F, Klafki HW, Ogorek I, Vogelgsang J, Wiltfang J, Scherbaum N, et al. Evaluation of cerebrospinal fluid glycoprotein NMB (GPNMB) as a potential biomarker for Alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimers Res Ther*. 2021;13(1):94.
11. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Biddle MS, Alshafie W, Fotouhi M, Bolivar SG, et al. Scaling of an antibody validation procedure enables quantification of antibody performance in major research applications. *Elife*. 2023;12.
12. Carter AJ, Kraemer O, Zwick M, Mueller-Fahrnow A, Arrowsmith CH, Edwards AM. Target 2035: probing the human proteome. *Drug Discov Today*. 2019;24(11):2111-5.
13. Licciardello MP, Workman P. The era of high-quality chemical probes. *RSC Medicinal Chemistry*. 2022;13(12):1446-59.
14. Ayoubi R, Ryan J, Bolivar SG, Alende C, Moleon VR, Fotouhi M, et al. A consensus platform for antibody characterization (Version 1). *Protocol Exchange*. 2024.
15. Biddle MS, Virk HS. YCharOS open antibody characterisation data: Lessons learned and progress made F1000Research 2023. 2023;12:1344.
16. Laflamme C, McKeever PM, Kumar R, Schwartz J, Kolaoudouzan M, Chen CX, et al. Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72. *Elife*. 2019;8.
17. Fire A, Xu S, Montgomery MK, Kostas SA, Driver SE, Mello CC. Potent and specific genetic interference by double-stranded RNA in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Nature*. 1998;391(6669):806-11.
18. Dana H, Chalbatani GM, Mahmoodzadeh H, Karimloo R, Rezaiean O, Moradzadeh A, et al. Molecular Mechanisms and Biological Functions of siRNA. *Int J Biomed Sci*. 2017;13(2):48-57.
19. Bandrowski A, Pairish M, Eckmann P, Grethe J, Martone ME. The Antibody Registry: ten years of registering antibodies. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 2023;51(D1):D358-d67.
20. Bairoch A. The Cellosaurus, a Cell-Line Knowledge Resource. *J Biomol Tech*. 2018;29(2):25-38.
21. Stringer C, Wang T, Michaelos M, Pachitariu M. Cellpose: a generalist algorithm for cellular segmentation. *Nat Methods*. 2021;18(1):100-6.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
ATCC	HTB-14	CVCL_0022	U-87 MG	WT

Table 2: Summary of the GPNMB antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab175427*	GR3302904-13	AB_3096346	monoclonal	7C10E5	mouse	1.00	Wb
Abcam	ab222109**	GR3233442-2	AB_2941017	recombinant-mono	EPR22011-11	rabbit	0.53	Wb
Abcam	ab227695**	GR3209303-9	AB_2924286	recombinant-mono	SP299	rabbit	n/a	Wb
Abcam	ab235873**	GR3233451-1	AB_3096344	recombinant-mono	EPR22011-47	rabbit	0.51	Wb
ABclonal	A14270	106890101	AB_2761133	polyclonal		rabbit	2.79	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP44499	QC76439-210609	AB_1294281	polyclonal		rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP44500	QC75988-210209	AB_2046124	polyclonal		rabbit	0.50	Wb
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP44501	QC58822-190922	AB_10641681	polyclonal		rabbit	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	AF2550	UYK0422121	AB_416615	polyclonal		goat	0.00	Wb
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB2550*	WFQ0218091	AB_2112939	monoclonal	303802	mouse	0.50	Wb
Bio-Techne (R&D Systems)	MAB25501*	WLZ0223041	AB_2112938	monoclonal	303822	mouse	0.50	Wb, IF
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP2-37351*	151104	AB_3094822	monoclonal	7C10E5	mouse	1.00	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	13251**	1	AB_2798162	recombinant-mono	E1Y7J	rabbit	n/a	Wb, IP
Cell Signaling Technology	38313**	1	AB_2799131	recombinant-mono	E4D7P	rabbit	0.07	Wb, IP
GeneTex	GTX103277	40688	AB_11165150	polyclonal		rabbit	1.00	Wb
Proteintech	20338-1-AP	19129	AB_10667459	polyclonal		rabbit	0.26	Wb
Proteintech	66926-1-Ig*	10011143	AB_2882253	monoclonal	2B10B8	mouse	1.90	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-24014*	WJ3416965	AB_2607806	monoclonal	303822	mouse	0.50	Wb, IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-38532*	YE3913329	AB_2898444	monoclonal	7C10E5	mouse	1.00	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-49360**	H681860016	AB_3075017	recombinant-mono	PSH0-82	rabbit	1.00	Wb

Wb= western blot; IF= immunofluorescence; IP= immunoprecipitation, *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody, n/a= not available

Table 3: Illustrations to assess antibody performance in all western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence

Western blot			Immunoprecipitation			Immunofluorescence		
Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	Successful antibody	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody	WT/KO cell mosaic	Successful antibody	Unsuccessful antibody
WT KO	WT KO	WT KO	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	SM UB IP	WT KO	WT KO	WT KO
<p>kDa 245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein detected (arrowhead)</p>	<p>kDa 245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein detected (arrowhead) among others</p>	<p>kDa 245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein not detected</p>	<p>kDa 245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein captured in the IP</p>	<p>kDa 245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein captured in the IP</p>	<p>kDa 245- 135- 75- 48- 25- 11-</p> <p>Target protein not captured in the IP</p>		<p>Target protein detected (white staining)</p>	<p>Target protein not detected</p>

This table has been reproduced with permission from Ayoubi et al., Elife, 2023 (11)

Figure 1: GPMB antibody screening by western blot (1/2)

Figure 2: GPNMB antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (1/2)

Figure 2: GPNMB antibody screening by immunoprecipitation (2/2)

Figure 3: GPNMB antibody screening by immunofluorescence (1/2)

Figure 3: GPNMB antibody screening by immunofluorescence (2/2)

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: GPNMB antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of U-87 MG ctrl and *GPNMB* KD were prepared, and 60 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated GPNMB antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of ctrl and KD lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilution used: ab175427* at 1/1000, ab222109** at 1/1000, ab227695** at 1/500, ab235873** at 1/500, A14270 at 1/500, ARP44499 at 1/500, ARP44500 at 1/500, ARP44501 at 1/500, AF2550 at 1/500, MAB2550* at 1/500, MAB25501* at 1/500, NBP2-37351* at 1/500, 13251** at 1/500, 38313** at 1/500, GTX103277 at 1/500, 20338-1-AP at 1/500, 66926-1-Ig* at 1/5000, MA5-24014* at 1/500, MA5-38532* at 1/200, MA5-49360** at 1/1000. Some antibodies were titrated as the signal was too weak when following the supplier's recommendations. Predicted band size: 63.9 kDa *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody, ctrl= control, KD= knockdown.

Figure 2: GPNMB antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

U-87 MG WT lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 1 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated GPNMB antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the indicated GPNMB antibody. For western blot, antibody 38313** was used at 1/500. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=6% starting material; UB=6% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate, n/s= non-specific signal. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 3: GPNMB antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

U-87 MG ctrl and *GPNMB* KD cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. Ctrl and KD cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio on coverslips. Cells were stained with the indicated GPNMB antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (ctrl), red (antibody staining) and far-red (KD) channels was performed. Representative images of the merged blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. Ctrl and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. When an antibody was recommended for immunofluorescence by the supplier, we tested it at the recommended dilution. The rest of the antibodies were tested at 1 and 2 µg/ml and the final concentration was selected based on the detection range of the microscope used and a quantitative analysis not shown here. Antibody dilution used: ab175427* at 1/500, ab222109** at 1/250, ab227695** at 1/500, ab235873** at 1/250, A14270 at 1/2000, ARP44499 at 1/250, ARP44500 at 1/250, ARP44501 at 1/250, AF2550 at 1/1000, MAB2550* at 1/500, MAB25501* at 1/250, NBP2-37351* at 1/500, 13251** at 1/500, 38313** at 1/35, GTX103277 at 1/500, 20338-1-AP at 1/250, 66926-1-Ig* at 1/2000, MA5-24014* at 1/500, MA5-38532* at 1/100, MA5-49360** at 1/1000. Bars = 10 µm. *= monoclonal antibody, **= recombinant antibody.